

OCEAN MONITORING IN SUPPORT OF FISHERIES RESEARCH AND MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

Monitoring of fluctuations of ocean conditions in time and space is vital for understanding fluctuations of marine populations. Three scales of temporal and spatial resolution are desired: 1) global, long term annual and monthly mean data for planning surveys and for understanding distributions of populations, 2) regional, monthly data to understand and predict annual recruitment and catches, and 3) mesoscale, daily data for research on biological processes and as tactical support for fishing vessels. Due to high costs of operation, monitoring on the largest two scales is not feasible with research vessels. Monitoring is possible, however, using a mix of surface weather and XBT observations from ships of opportunity, tide gauge data, observations from moored and drifting buoys, and remote sensing images from satellites.

I. INTRODUCTION

A common characteristic of fisheries is that the populations undergo large fluctuations from year to year and thus a major problem for fisheries and management research is to understand and eventually to predict fluctuations of populations. Population sizes are affected by many factors including: 1) environmental conditions, 2) factors related to the fishery, such as the total catch and its distribution, and 3) interactions with other species. A key factor causing changes in populations is fluctuations of recruitment, that is, the number of young fish recruited into a fishery each year. This factor may vary by two or more orders of magnitude between years. The problem is also complicated by the fact that fish have evolved to occupy certain very specific ecological niches in the ocean. Each fish species has evolved a complex life history to exploit its ecological niche and to adapt to the temporal and spatial fluctuations of the niche. Because of the wide variety of possible ecological niches in the ocean, we observe a wide variety of fish life histories. Some fish are benthic, some are coastal, some oceanic, some are resident in one area, and some migrate long distances during their lives.

Understanding and modeling of marine fish populations is thus very difficult because of the many and varied physical and biological processes

that affect the populations. To simplify the problem, biologists have often assumed steady state environmental conditions. These models are normally for single species and work for very long term average conditions but completely ignore interactions between species and year-to-year fluctuations that are vitally important in many fisheries. To include these effects, attempts have been made to model interactions of populations with their entire ecosystems. Because of our limited understanding of the numerous dynamic processes involved, such models have had limited success. A more promising approach has been to try to model direct physical effects of the environment on fish populations and ignore the uncertainties of the biological processes. Even with this simplification, a limiting factor in modeling has been our inability to understand and describe the various physical effects of the ocean in sufficient detail.

For studies of populations and recruitment, we typically get only one data point per year and thus require long time series of historical data on ocean fluctuations, obtained for periods of decades or longer. For other fisheries problems, shorter term data are useable. There are typically three scales of resolution of ocean processes needed for fisheries purposes as shown in Figure 1. The data must be collected at sufficiently high data rates to resolve pertinent fluctuations with as few gaps in coverage as possible. The environmental data series must also be updated within a few months or so of the time of data collection if the data are to be useable for monitoring current ocean conditions and for use in annual fishery forecasts.

The data coverage should be high in regions of fishery interest such as within the 200 mile zone around the United States but other areas must be monitored as well. Similar data are needed near other coastlines for international cooperative programs and for comparative studies of similar ecosystems. Oceanic species such as tuna are found in much of the tropic and temperate oceans and require environmental data. Interest in high latitude species such as Antarctic krill is also increasing and thus ocean monitoring must be global in coverage.

Because of their availability and low cost, time series of air temperatures at land stations and sea surface temperatures from coastal stations have been used for correlation studies. The resulting

correlations have often held for several years and then fallen down, indicating that additional factors such as offshore or deep conditions need to be considered. Traditionally, it has been common to use research vessels to monitor offshore conditions and to merge data collected by several different vessels in different years and months to form composite maps of conditions. Such maps can give only very general pictures of the true ocean variability as the data were not observed simultaneously in a synoptic manner. Due to the limitations of ship speeds and numbers of available ships, such surveys have not been adequate to describe the ocean conditions on the time and space scales that may affect fish populations. With present day high vessel operating costs, monitoring programs that are based on research vessels are being phased out. An example of this is the CalCOFI program of hydrographic surveys off California which is now being phased out after over 25 years of data collection. Research vessels continue to be used only when they are the only possible method of data collection, such as for special surveys and experiments.

For ocean monitoring on the long time and space scales, we need to observe the ocean as a time-space continuum and not just as a series of independent surveys. We need to develop a routine, operational ocean monitoring system comparable to that of the atmosphere that the meteorologists now almost take for granted. For this monitoring, we can no longer rely on research vessels but instead must turn to automated observing platforms for data collection. At present, our only ocean monitoring data come from a variety of data sources and observing platforms including ships of opportunity, research vessel cruises, tide gauges, buoys, satellites, and others. The data collection is not integrated in any systematic way and a major problem is to develop techniques to merge the available data from the diverse sources.

To make the problem more difficult, many of the data that are collected are not available in digital form in a reasonable time and thus timely preparation of ocean monitoring products based on the combined data is not possible. Many of the data are submitted to the National Oceanographic Data Center here in Washington but there is commonly a delay of a year or more in data submission. Many of the remaining data are never submitted to NODC at all. Delays also occur in the processing and distribution of the data to users. A major improvement of the ocean monitoring could be made just by reporting and processing more of the existing data in a more timely manner. One way this is being accomplished is to merge ocean data processing with existing real-time processing of meteorological data at weather forecasting centers such as NOAA's National Meteorological Center here in Washington and the Navy's Fleet Numerical Oceanography Center in Monterey.

II. OCEAN MONITORING DATA SOURCES

Surface weather reports from ships of opportunity such as merchant and naval ships are our most common source of ocean monitoring data but

are primarily designed to serve meteorological needs. Figure 2 shows the distribution of sea surface temperature observations from ships, primarily in the Northern Hemisphere, during October 1979 as received by Fleet Numerical Oceanography Center. These observations have been made globally since the 1850's and thus long time series data are available. The reports are radioed to shore analysis centers in near real-time under a program of the World Meteorological Organization. The data allow monitoring of marine climatic conditions and modeling of the dominant atmospheric processes driving ocean fluctuations. These processes include wind stress from which Ekman transport and coastal upwelling indices are derived and air - sea heat exchange processes computed from temperature, humidity and wind data.

There are a number of problems with use of surface weather observations for ocean monitoring. One is that errors in encoding and transmitting the reports can cause errors in the time and position of the observations. These errors cause the sea surface temperature reports from land areas as shown in the figure. A second problem is that although surface marine meteorological observations are reasonably complete along the major shipping lanes, there are vast areas of the oceans where shipping is sparse and from which few observations are available. Another problem is the lack of accurate, calibrated sensors for sea surface temperature and winds on most merchant ships. Whereas the Port Meteorological Officers check and calibrate the ships' barometers and psychrometers, sea surface temperature is commonly measured with crude, uncalibrated instruments. Winds are often estimated by the appearance of the sea surface rather than by anemometers. When winds are observed with anemometers, vector corrections of the data for the speed and direction of the ship are usually made manually and errors are common. A fourth problem is that radio reporting of the observations to shore by Morse Code is slow and error prone. Regular reporting of the data on a 6 hourly basis requires that the ship's radio officer be on duty for each transmission and thus nighttime synoptic radio messages are less abundant than day time ones. Automatic devices to record and transmit the weather reports to shore analysis centers by satellite are needed to alleviate many of these problems.

A second and promising source of monitoring data is drifting buoys. Satellite tracked drifting buoys were deployed in large numbers in the Southern Hemisphere in 1979 by the First GARP Global Experiment (FGGE) to compensate for the lack of ship observations there. The buoys were instrumented to measure atmospheric pressure and sea surface temperature and report their data by satellite in near real-time. The drifting buoy tracks are seen in the figure. As a part of research programs, many drifting buoys have also been released in recent years but the research buoys do not normally report data in real-time to weather forecasting centers and so do not appear in the figure. Drifting buoys can be very useful in monitoring ocean currents in that their drift automatically integrates the currents over time and thus a track

of daily positions of a drifting buoy contains only the lower frequency components of the currents. The relatively low cost of drifting buoys permits deployment in large numbers such as was done by FGGE.

Moored "monster buoys" offer a third source of ocean monitoring data. Moored buoys are much more expensive than drifting buoys because of their higher initial costs and because they must be periodically serviced by surface vessels. Moored buoys are excellent platforms for time series observation of surface and subsurface conditions. In the past few years, moored buoys have been deployed along the east and west coasts of the United States by the NOAA Data Buoy Office with support from the Bureau of Land Management. The data are radioed to shore in near real-time. Figure 3 shows time series data from a moored buoy off Oregon during 1978. The data appear very useful but are marred by instrument failures which cause serious gaps in time coverage. To remedy the data gap problem, redundant sensors should be installed on the buoys.

A fourth source of ocean monitoring data is that provided by tide gages at coastal and island locations. Tide gages are ideal for ocean monitoring as they are inexpensive, are widely installed over the globe, and because sea level is an integrated index of ocean density structure and circulation. In addition, many tide gages have long data records, some extending back into the 1800's. Dr. Klaus Wyrtki at the University of Hawaii has extensively investigated sea level fluctuations in the tropical Pacific and has shown that equatorial currents can be monitored from sea level data. Off California, we are finding that sea level and time series of dynamic height computed from frequent hydrographic stations are closely correlated and that both data series appear to be responding to fluctuations of the nearshore, northward flowing Davidson Current.

Images of the ocean surface from orbiting satellites provide a fifth ocean monitoring data source and offer excellent spatial resolution of a number of features including clouds, sea surface temperature, optical properties of the water, and various atmospheric radiation components. Ocean circulation patterns are easily observed in infrared and color scanner maps. Satellite data are available globally and are processed by the National Environmental Satellite Service and others in near real-time. Scatterometer measurements of wind speed and direction such as those made by SEASAT can provide much more detailed information on the distribution of ocean winds than can be obtained by widely spaced platforms such as merchant ships. In the future, the ocean color scanner will be very valuable for monitoring circulation patterns and satellite altimetry measurements may allow long term monitoring of ocean currents. Satellite data have certain disadvantages, however, including gaps in coverage due to atmospheric effects. A second problem is that the volume of satellite data can overwhelm data processing systems and limit the ability of the systems to handle the data. At present, satellite data are not useful for long term

studies as satellites have only been available for a decade or so and thus no long historical data series exist. The spatial images are not easily reduced to objective indices for use in time series analyses.

The monitoring systems mentioned so far provide primarily ocean surface data, or as is the case of sea level, an integrated picture of certain ocean conditions. What is more important, however, is information on subsurface conditions, particularly on the temperature structure. The most important of these is the subsurface temperature structure as oceanographers are finding that the depth of the thermocline can vary markedly in time and space and is closely related to ocean circulation changes. Ocean temperature data can thus be used to infer geostrophic flow in areas where the effect of salinity on the density structure is relatively stable. The Navy is particularly interested in subsurface temperature because of its effects on the velocity of sound in water and thus on the operation of sonar equipment. Over the large sections of the oceans that have regular shipping, subsurface temperature can be monitored from merchant ships by expendable bathythermograph or XBT. Such monitoring has been done since World War II, (formerly using mechanical BT's) from research and military vessels. The development of the XBT in the 1960's permitted the expansion of the monitoring to merchant ships which spend more of their time in mid-ocean areas than do most research and military vessels.

Because of their interest in global subsurface temperature mapping, Fleet Numerical Oceanography Center has developed a Cooperative Oceanic Observations Program which has installed XBT observing equipment on about 50 ships of opportunity. These data, together with XBT data from various research programs using ships of opportunity now provide the basis of our global subsurface ocean monitoring. Additional observations are made by other techniques such as mechanical BT's, bottle casts, and STD profiles. Many of the data are being sent in real-time by the Integrated Global Ocean Station System (IGOSS) to Fleet Numerical Oceanography Center in Monterey and to National Meteorological Center here in Washington. Transmittal of the strip chart or digital data to NODC is often delayed for several months or years and thus for ocean monitoring within a month or so of real-time, the radio messages of XBT observations are the primary source of available data.

Recently NOAA and the Navy have agreed to cooperate on expansion of the Navy's XBT program to global sampling. NOAA is primarily interested in obtaining a global distribution of observations in support of climate research while the Navy is increasingly interested in monitoring ocean conditions globally, including the Southern Hemisphere. The two agencies are now surveying their needs in an attempt to determine an optimum sampling pattern to achieve the goals of both agencies at reasonable cost.

A problem with conventional analog strip chart XBT recorders on ships of opportunity is the requirement that the observer, who is typically a

volunteer and a ship's officer, must manually read the trace and prepare a message for radio transmission to shore by Morse Code. Preparation of a radio message takes 15 minutes or so of the officer's time and thus the officers are reluctant to make more than 2 XBT drops per day. Prototype automated shipboard XBT digitizing systems using microcomputers have been developed to reduce operator involvement. Communication of data to shore will be via satellite to reduce data garbles during transmission. A second problem is the cost of XBT probes which now cost at least \$35 each. Development of a retrievable electronic BT which could operate to depths of 300 to 400 meters and at ship speeds of 10 to 15 knots would allow more closely spaced observations at reasonable cost.

Currents and water circulation are parameters that are particularly needed for fisheries and climate research. While observing ocean currents from drifting buoys and satellites is very promising, at present the only global standard, routine method of observing ocean currents is by ship drift -- that is, the difference between a ship's actual position after a several hour run and the estimated position by dead reckoning. Most of the presently available ship drift observations were made prior to World War II by sextant sightings and contain sizable uncertainties due to the astronomical navigation fixes. Today when many ships have satellite navigation receivers, we have a unique opportunity to improve the number and quality of ship drift observations. The required data for ship drift computations are already available to the microprocessors in the satellite navigation receivers so all that needs to be done is to program the processors to compute ship drift current observations and store them for timely transmission to shore. The resulting reports would be used to develop ocean current charts which would be very useful for a variety of applications such as navigation and fisheries.

III. CONCLUSION

Ocean monitoring provides a good example of the needed partnership of government, industry, and academia at which this conference is aimed. Continued cooperation between the three partners is needed to develop a coherent, integrated ocean monitoring program based on the available data sources. The program must sample globally on the various scales of resolution of interest. The program must be low in cost so as to continue for many years and to be able to weather the inevitable budget crises. Because of the requirement for low cost, we must rely on volunteer observers and to an increasing extent on automated observing platforms. When volunteer observers are required, the equipment must be simple, reliable, and involve only a minimal amount of manual record keeping. Time and position data, for example, must be semi-automatic. The program must also be internationally coordinated because ocean monitoring is too big a problem for the United States alone and thus should be coordinated with similar efforts of other nations.

Research programs at universities have developed ocean monitoring techniques and have run monitoring programs for several years and shown the value of the data. Now the ocean monitoring efforts need to be transferred to operational government agencies which can operate them for extended periods. A second function of universities is to evaluate the data for accuracy and reasonableness. At least a minimal level of quality control has to be done by the monitoring agency but a very useful function of universities is to use the data in research projects and thus to provide critical evaluation of the data. Universities also will continue to develop new techniques to improve the data collection and new analysis schemes to improve the quality and utility of the data. Of particular importance are development of analysis techniques that can merge data from the various data sources to form more coherent pictures of ocean fluctuations.

The role of industry in ocean monitoring is vital in that the monitoring equipment needs to be improved, made more reliable, and made available at reasonable cost. Reliability of equipment cannot be emphasized too highly. Unless the equipment operates reliably in a harsh environment with little or no maintenance, data quality will suffer and undesirable gaps in the data will occur. Standardization of equipment globally is also important so that data are comparable over the entire ocean. Equipment on ships of opportunity must be standardized because ships are met and equipment serviced in many different ports by employees of various agencies. Standardization of interfaces between various monitoring devices is required so that units can be combined in various ways without the presently common interfacing problems. Compatibility of data storage media between devices should be encouraged.

An improved ability to monitor ocean variability will be of great value in climate research and prediction, in defense applications, and in applications to research and management of marine resources. In fisheries management, improved measures of ocean variability will permit studies of environmental effects on the abundance and distribution of fish populations. Improved understanding of environment-fishery relationships will aid in establishing fishery management procedures that should provide for a more sustainable yield of valuable and renewable fishery resources.

<u>Space Scale</u>	<u>Time Scale</u>	<u>Fisheries Application</u>
Global and ocean wide	Annual and monthly longterm mean values	Planning surveys Research on distribution of populations Migration studies
Regional	Individual monthly mean values	Forecasting annual recruitment and catch Regional studies
Local	Hourly, daily, or weekly values Environmental quality studies	Fishing tactics of individual vessels

Figure 1. Scales of resolution needed for ocean monitoring for fisheries purposes.

Figure 2 - Global distribution of sea surface temperature reports received by Fleet Numerical Oceanography Center during November 1979 from ships (primarily in Northern Hemisphere) and from drifting buoys (primarily in Southern Hemisphere).

Figure 3 - Time series data observed by National Data Buoy Office moored buoy 46005 off Oregon in 1978. Time series are surface wind vectors, zonal and meridional wind stress, air temperature, and sea surface temperature. Note gaps in the sea surface temperature record which reduce the utility of the data.